

Naked Fragment

What brought me here today was always listening to that small voice inside me.

The one in the middle of all the others. The one in the middle of all the confusion.

The one that never betrayed me.

My actions always seemed incoherent to others.

I never really knew where I was going. And I still don't.

But I am here today.

I don't know if what I did will ever serve humanity.

I have no idea. Maybe in 20 years, maybe in 50, maybe never.

It led me to be violated at the deepest level of my soul

by almost every being I cherished.

Often in ways far worse than what I thought was the worst.

But I kept going. I am still here.

Being crushed by my own family.

Being seen as mentally deficient.

And watching them slowly collapse into dementia, dissociation,
and withdrawal from life day by day.

And yet still loving them.

Spending dozens of hours in winter in the cold

just so they wouldn't see my total collapse.

Because I had a physical roof, yes —

but not a roof in the metaphorical sense.

I had no place of rest.

And my brother — he is in a state

you wouldn't wish on anyone in your family.

Seeing and understanding each of them,

not abandoning them even if they abandoned me.

That is life.

Why do you see me as a myth?

As something exceptional?

When I am simply simple.

In the beginning I hoped to receive money

so I wouldn't have to work just to survive.

To share it with my friends, my family.

I hoped to obtain medical help for all those I love who need it.

Yes — that was true.

I hoped to help humanity

and leave no soul behind.

That has always been sincere.

Now I see that the spiritual experts
and followers of Krishnamurti are not.
They crush life itself.

Today, I don't know.
I don't know if I'm being read.
I know nothing.

And that is what it is.

I don't know why I'm writing this fragment.
And yet I write it.
Totally naked.